

LAND COVER CLASSIFICATION ENHANCEMENT BY TRAINING SAMPLES SEPARATION: A CASE STUDY FOR LAND DEGRADATION INDICATION

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Land cover is a fundamental land surface parameter considered a key indicator of land degradation processes. Changes in land cover indicate a reduction or increase in vegetation, habitat fragmentation and land conversion as triggers of land degradation. The rate of land cover changes also indicates the intensity of the degradation processes.

Land cover mapping is generally derived from Earth observation and requires reliable and comparable classification techniques. However, despite the wide range of land cover classification techniques and information products, enhanced land cover mapping is still challenging, especially for highly heterogeneous natural areas and areas with different agricultural or functional land use types.

In this study, we propose two approaches to enhance land cover classification for land degradation indication, namely:

- training samples clustering;
- input dataset optimization.

The first approach aims to lessen the subjectiveness of expert-selected classes and training samples mixing. This point is reached by the application of unsupervised methods to perform clustering of classes training samples.

The second approach implies the selection of the input dataset layers. Thus, it not only increases training samples separability but also decreases the initial number of dataset layers, reducing dataset volume.

Since each approach is presented as an optimization procedure and aims to increase the separability of the training samples, its objective function should quantify the separability. To assign the objective function, the Separability Index of Training Samples is developed.

The developed approaches were applied to enhance the land cover mapping of the heterogeneous natural landscapes in the case of the Shatsk National Natural Park. The experiment revealed that the land cover classification of the study area was enhanced by applying both of the developed approaches. This is evidenced by a 4% increase in overall accuracy from 77% to 81% with the training samples clustering. After input dataset optimization, overall accuracy was increased by 1% from 90 % to 91 %. Also, the dataset was reduced by 2.93 times from 167 to 57 layers.

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